

Essential and toxic elements in sustainable and underutilized seafood species and derived semi-industrial ready-to-eat products

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ABSTRACT

Blue whiting (*Micromesistius poutassou*), pouting (*Trisopterus luscus*) and common dab (*Limanda limanda*) are underutilized fish species attractive in terms of sustainability. However, there is limited information about their nutritional characteristics as well as potential presence of environmental contaminants. Specimens caught in European waters were characterised for their content of essential and toxic elements. The three species, along with common carp and blue mussels, relevant for sustainable production too, were employed as raw materials for the development of semi-industrial ready-to-eat products. Calcium, copper, iodine, iron, selenium, zinc, cadmium, lead, mercury, and nickel were determined by ICP-MS, whereas methylmercury was determined by HPLC-ICP-MS. These two techniques were also used to determine arsenic and inorganic arsenic, respectively, in blue mussel and derived products. Differences in element contents were related to the biology and ecology of the examined species. Intake of nutrients and exposure to contaminants were assessed in relation to the relevant DRVs and HBGVs, respectively. All the species were found to be valuable dietary sources of selenium. Pouting was rich in iodine and mussels were good sources of iodine and iron. These two species had comparatively higher levels of mercury and lead, respectively. However, the levels of contaminants were generally of no concern in both raw materials and products. Iodine bioaccessibility was studied in blue whiting, a species with an intermediate iodine content, and found to be 98%. Selenium:mercury molar ratios were assessed and found to be favourable. The semi-industrial products were found to be good sources of selenium and many of them provided appreciable amounts of calcium, iron, copper and zinc.

1. Introduction

Fish and seafood are sources of energy and protein with high biological value, and contribute to the intake of essential nutrients, such as trace elements and vitamins (especially A and D, and some B vitamins). Seafood is also a key source of n-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (n-3 LCPUFA), with well-established health benefits, and is a component of dietary patterns associated with good health (EFSA, 2014). Most European Food-Based Dietary Guidelines recommend a minimum of two servings of fish per week to ensure the provision of key nutrients, especially n-3 LCPUFA, but also vitamin D and trace elements such as selenium and iodine (marine species). The EFSA NDA Panel established that consumption of about 1–2 servings of seafood per week

and up to 3–4 servings per week during pregnancy is associated with better functional outcomes of neurodevelopment in children and with a lower risk of coronary heart disease mortality in adults compared to no consumption of seafood (EFSA, 2014).

Fish and seafood are also sources of exposure to environmental contaminants. Whereas risk-benefit analysis indicates that, in most cases, the benefits associated to fish and seafood consumption outweigh the risks, recommendations on seafood consumption for children and pregnant women refer to the type of fish also taking in account safety considerations, i.e. exposure to contaminants, methylmercury in the first place (EFSA, 2015; Thomsen et al., 2021). Indeed, available data indicate that not only the nutrient content of fish, but also the amount of methylmercury and other contaminants varies greatly among species

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(EFSA, 2015; FAO & WHO, 2011). Therefore, a proper characterization of the chemical ‘fingerprint’ of each species is relevant for an integrated assessment of both nutritional value and food safety.

If fish consumption is associated to considerable public health benefits, sustainability has become a key element to be considered when recommending the public to eat more seafood. Although aquatic food production has transitioned from being primarily based on wild fish capture to culture of farmed species, overexploitation of wild fish stocks is a global issue and affects several seafood species (HLPE, 2014; Bogard et al., 2019; FAO, 2020). For instance in the EU, where a limited number of species dominates seafood consumption, increasing and diversifying seafood production by utilizing nutrient-rich small fish, caught in the wild or farmed in a sustainable way, would be instrumental to improving human nutrition while achieving long-term sustainability outcomes (EEA, 2016).

Blue whiting (*Micromesistius poutassou*), pouting (*Trisopterus luscus*) and common dab (*Limanda limanda*) are currently underutilized fish species with a low to medium commercial value. Despite their potential as sustainable fish species (Table S1), information about their compositional and nutritional characteristics as well as potential presence of environmental contaminants is limited to absent. Within the SEA-FOOD^{TOMORROW} project (<https://seafoodtomorrow.eu/>) these species, along with common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) and blue mussels (*Mytilus edulis*), relevant for sustainable production as well according to current farming practices, were employed as raw materials for the development of semi-industrial ready-to-eat (RTE) products. They were designed to be affordable, appealing, and tasty food tailored to meet the needs of three different population groups, namely children (8–10 years old), pregnant women (20–40 years old) and seniors (≥ 60 years old), both in terms of nutrient supply and texture (e.g. absence of bones, easy to chew and shallow) (Oliveira et al., 2021).

In the present study, the five seafood species used in the productions of these innovative RTE products and the products themselves were characterised for their content of essential elements. In the raw foods, special emphasis was placed on selenium and iodine since fish and seafood may be valuable sources of these trace elements. In one selected species, namely blue whiting, iodine bioaccessibility (i.e. the amount of iodine that is released from the matrix and becomes available for absorption through the gut wall) was also studied by *in vitro* simulated human gastrointestinal digestion (Minekus et al., 2014). In addition, non-essential elements were determined, with a specific focus on mercury and methylmercury in the raw materials and the percentage of total mercury present as the most toxic, i.e. methylated, form (EFSA, 2012a). In blue mussel, the concentrations of total arsenic and inorganic arsenic, respectively, were also determined, since – contrary to finfish – shellfishes may contribute substantially to the exposure to the most toxic, i.e. inorganic, form of arsenic (Cubadda et al., 2016).

The nutritional value of the five seafood species, as well as the derived RTE foods, was assessed by determining the intake of calcium (Ca), copper (Cu), iodine (I), iron (Fe), selenium (Se), and zinc (Zn) provided in relation to the Dietary Reference Values (DRV) (EFSA, 2017). Exposure to the toxic elements – i.e. arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), mercury (Hg), and nickel (Ni) – and element species – i.e. methylmercury (MeHg), inorganic arsenic (iAs) – was also assessed and the associated risk characterised by comparison with the relevant Health Based Guidance Values (HBGV). In addition selenium:mercury molar ratios were evaluated since there is evidence that selenium, most likely when present in specific chemical forms, is able to interact with methylmercury and inactivate it by chemical binding and demethylation, thus providing an *in vivo* detoxification pathway (Manceau et al., 2021).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Fish and mussel samples

The five seafood species were collected in the European market. Blue

whiting (*Micromesistius poutassou*), pouting (*Trisopterus luscus*) and common dab (*Limanda limanda*) were caught in European waters, whereas common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) and blue mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) were obtained from farms located in France. Origin, market country, number of specimens, average length and total weight of the analytical sample are described in Table S2.

The samples were delivered to the laboratory frozen, sealed in plastic bags. The frozen samples were thawed and prepared for analysis as appropriate. For blue whiting, whole specimens were filleted using a ceramic knife. The other fish were obtained as fillets, whereas mussels were already deshelled. Individuals of each species were pooled and homogenized using a mixer with polypropylene cups and stainless steel knives. Three subsamples were collected from the pools to be submitted to analytical determinations.

2.2. Semi-industrial ready-to-eat products

Eco-innovative products based on the use of the five species detailed in 2.1 as raw materials were developed. The process leading to the design, formulation and production of the RTE foods is described in detail in Oliveira et al. (2021). Briefly, the ready-to-eat products were tailored to three population groups in terms of formulation and nutritional properties, as detailed in Table 1. Specific recipes (see Table 1) were selected by means of an international contest. The recipes were translated into semi-industrial RTE products at IDMer facilities by (i) replacing or removing ingredients in order to match the targeted nutritional criteria while preserving the organoleptic properties of the initial recipe and (ii) adapting the formulation with a view to the intended frozen storage (and subsequent defrosting and heating, e.g. microwaving, prior to consumption). The final semi-industrial RTE products were manufactured as portions of 250 g each, frozen and vacuum skin-packed in PP trays (23.5 × 15 × 2.5 cm). Their proximate chemical composition, energy value and content of several nutrients (n-3 LCPUFA, potassium, sodium, vitamins B12, E, D3, and iodine) is

Table 1
Seafood-based semi-industrial ready-to-eat (RTE) products.

Target population groups	Biological species ^a	Brief description of the recipe	Derived RTE product	RTE product short name
Children (8–10 years old)	<i>Trisopterus luscus</i> (29%)	Pouting fish balls with sweet potato and banana purée and crispy banana	Fish balls with a puree	FisBall_C
	<i>Cyprinus carpio</i> (31%)	Carp sausages with vegetables accompanied by salad and baked sweet potatoes	Fish sausage with vegetables	FisSau_C
Pregnant women (20–40 years old)	<i>Micromesistius poutassou</i> (31%)	Blue whiting and cabbage roulade with boiled potatoes	Fish roulade	FisRou_P
	<i>Limanda limanda</i> (37%)	Sauteed common dab with wheat berry salad	Fish fillet with wheat salad	FisFil_P
Seniors (≥ 60 years old)	<i>Mytilus edulis</i> (11%) and <i>Micromesistius poutassou</i> (11%)	Hearty mussel soup with fish stock, root and tuber vegetables	Mussel soup with fish stock	MusSou_S
	<i>Micromesistius poutassou</i> (25%)	Blue whiting fish balls with vegetables and marinara sauce	Fish balls with vegetables and sauce	FisBall_S

^a Proportion of the final product (% w/w) indicated in parenthesis.

described in Oliveira et al. (2021).

Finally, an alternative formulation of MusSou_S, consisting in the same recipe but with the use of shelled mussels (ExtraSou_S), was investigated.

For each RTE product, three independent samples were analysed. The content of the entire sample was homogenized using a mixer with polypropylene cups and stainless steel knives (in the case of ExtraSou_S after removing the shells). At least two subsamples were collected from the pools and submitted to analytical determinations.

2.3. Analytical methods

2.3.1. Total element determinations

Sample handling was carried out in clean room conditions. For both the raw materials and the RTE homogenized samples, 1 g subsamples were placed in high-pressure Teflon containers with 3 mL of HNO₃ 67–69% v/v (ultrapure grade, Carlo Erba, Rodano, Italy) and 1 mL of H₂O₂ 30% v/v (ultrapure grade, Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany). Samples were digested in a microwave system (UltraWAVE Single Reaction Chamber Microwave Digestion System, Milestone, Bergamo, Italy) with the following program: 23 min 240 °C ramp, 10 min 240 °C hold (maximum power 1400 W), 30 min depressurization and cooling at room temperature. For analytical quality control, several certified reference materials were included in each analytical batch (certified/reference values and found values are shown in Table S3).

The standard solutions and internal standards were obtained by diluting stock solutions (1 g L⁻¹) (High-Purity, Charleston, SC, USA) with ultrapure water (Product Water Resistivity 18.2 MΩ cm, TOC ≤ 2 µg L⁻¹) obtained from a Milli-Q Element system (Millipore, Molsheim, France). Total concentrations of As, Ca, Cd, Cu, Fe, Hg, Ni, Pb, Se, Zn were determined by means of a triple quadrupole inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS/MS) (Agilent 8800, Agilent Technologies Inc., Tokyo, Japan) equipped with a PFA concentric nebulizer and a double-pass PFA spray chamber cooled to 2 °C. The system was operated in standard and MS/MS mode using He as collision gas to provide interference-free detection of the analytes. The LODs and LOQs achieved are shown in Table S4.

The conditions used for all elements except mercury and iodine are summarized in Table S5. For total mercury determination, the standards and samples at their final dilution were added before analysis with Au so as to obtain a gold-mercury amalgam. The optimized concentration of Au (100 µg L⁻¹) prevented mercury losses and memory effects. The conditions used are summarized in Table S6. For iodine determination, standards and samples were prepared in 0.5% (v/v) ammonia (Sigma Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany) and 1% (v/v) isopropanol (Sigma Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany). To prevent memory effects, a quartz nebulizer and spray chamber were used and 0.5% (v/v) tetramethylammonium hydroxide TraceSelect (Sigma Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany) was used for washing the sample introduction system. A Nexion 350D ICP-MS (PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA, USA) was employed. The conditions used are summarized in Table S7.

2.3.2. Speciation analysis

The extraction of mercury species was carried out by means of a mixture containing thiol compounds, i.e. 0.20% (v/v) 2-mercaptoethanol (Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany) and 0.20% (w/v) L-cysteine (Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany), with 1% (v/v) HCl (ultrapure grade, Carlo Erba, Rodano, Italy). Samples (1 g) were placed in previously decontaminated amber scintillation vials, added with 20 mL of extracting mixture and placed in an ultrasonic bath at 40 °C for 30 min. After extraction the sample was centrifuged, the supernatant recovered and filtered on 0.45 µm PVDF membranes. The extracted samples were immediately injected for speciation analysis. A Nexion 350D ICP-MS mass spectrometer (PerkinElmer, Norwalk, CT) was combined on line with a PerkinElmer Series 200 metal-free HPLC system and used as element selective detector. The exit of the column was directly

connected by means of PEEK capillary tubing to the quartz concentric nebulizer of the ICP-MS. For methylmercury (MeHg), a stock solution of 200 mg mL⁻¹ was prepared by dissolving in water adequate amounts of methylmercury chloride Pestanal (Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany). The standard solution for inorganic mercury was obtained by diluting a 1 g L⁻¹ stock solution (High-Purity, Charleston, SC, USA) with high-purity deionized water. To prevent loss of the analytes, all dilutions were carried out in amber glass vials, previously decontaminated. The conditions used are summarized in Table S8. Methylmercury concentrations are expressed as mercury throughout.

For arsenic speciation analysis, 0.35 g of samples were added with 10 mL of 1% (v/v) HNO₃ and 1% (v/v) H₂O₂ and left to stand overnight. Inorganic arsenic was solubilised using an heating bath with stirring for 1 h, at 95 °C. The extracts were centrifuged (15 min, 10000 rpm, 4 °C) and the supernatants filtered (0.22 µm). With the extraction procedure used, As(III) is converted to As(V), which appears as a well separated peak in the anion exchange HPLC-ICP-MS chromatogram. The same instrumental setup described for mercury speciation was used. The ArCl interference at *m/z* 75 was assessed by monitoring *m/z* 37 and 77. The conditions used are summarized in Table S9.

2.4. Iodine bioaccessibility

Iodine bioaccessibility was assessed by the standardised static *in vitro* simulated human gastrointestinal digestion model of Minekus et al. (2014). The *in vitro* digestion protocol used is summarized in Figure S1. Three digestion fluids were used, i.e. saliva, gastric, and intestinal fluids, at the conditions shown in Figure S1. All reagents were standard analytical grade, enzymes were provided by Sigma Aldrich.

2.5. Intake assessment of essential elements

For the fish species and mussels, the intake resulting from the consumption of a 100 g portion was calculated (WHO & FAO, 2011; EFSA, 2015). For the RTE products, the intake resulting from the consumption of a single portion (250 g) was calculated. These intakes were considered in the light of the dietary reference values the DRVs established by EFSA (2017) according to the following formula:

$$\% DRV = \frac{C \times M}{DRV} \times 100$$

where:

C is the mean concentration of the element (µg/g); *M* is the weight of the food item (g); *DRV* is the population reference intake (PRI) in the case of calcium, iron, zinc and the adequate intake (AI) for copper, iodine and selenium. The PRIs and AIs considered were those of adults in the case of the raw products, and those of the relevant population groups for the RTE products. For zinc, the PRI corresponding to a level of phytate intake of 600 mg/d was considered. For iron, the PRI of post-menopausal women was considered for female seniors. The DRVs used are summarized in Table S10.

2.6. Exposure assessment of non-essential elements

Parallel to the approach adopted for essential elements, the daily exposure was calculated from the consumption of a 100 g portion of fish species and mussels or a 250 g portion of RTE products. These exposures were compared to the HBGVs established by EFSA according to the following formula:

$$\% HBGV = \frac{C \times M}{HBGV} \times 100$$

where:

C is the mean concentration of the element (µg/g); *M* is the weight of the food item (g); *HBGV* is one of the following: the lowest BMDL₀₁ of

0.3 µg/kg bw/day for inorganic arsenic (EFSA, 2009a), the TWI of 1.3 µg/kg bw/week – expressed on a daily basis – for methylmercury (EFSA, 2012a), the TWI of 2.5 µg/kg bw/week – expressed on a daily basis – for cadmium (EFSA, 2009b), the BMDL₀₁ of 0.63 µg/kg bw/day (for nephrotoxicity) for lead – since the lowest BMDL₀₁ of 0.5 µg/kg bw/day for developmental neurotoxicity is relevant only for young children up to the age of 7 – (EFSA, 2010), the TDI of 13 µg/kg bw/day for nickel (EFSA, 2020). In addition to chronic toxicity, nickel may raise concerns also because of acute effects, i.e. eczematous flare-up reactions elicited by oral intake in already sensitized individuals, a condition known as systemic contact dermatitis (SCD). The exposure resulting from a single occasion of consumption was thus compared with the lowest-observed-adverse-effect-level (LOAEL) of 4.3 µg Ni/kg bw by means of the margin of exposure (MOE) approach, where a MOE of 30 or higher was considered as being indicative of a low health concern (EFSA, 2020). A MOE approach was used also for inorganic arsenic and lead, according to the EFSA assessments (EFSA, 2009a; EFSA, 2009b).

A body weight of 80 kg was used for male adults (including seniors), whereas a body weight of 70 kg was used for female adults (including pregnant women) (values from EFSA, 2012b rounded to the nearest ten). For children aged 8–10, a body weight of 30 kg was used.

2.7. Statistical analysis

Concentrations were reported as means and standard deviations. Methylmercury and inorganic arsenic concentrations were expressed as element (Hg and As, respectively), and their ratio to total mercury and total arsenic were expressed as percentage (%). Se:Hg molar ratios uncertainty was calculated by propagation of uncertainty considering the standard deviations of Se and Hg.

The LODs (LOQs) were calculated on the basis of the 3σ (6 σ) criterion, where σ is the standard deviation of the measurement of 20 method blanks.

The comparisons between found values and certified or reference values of CRMs were carried out by estimating the expanded uncertainty with a coverage factor of 2 (corresponding to a level of confidence of 95%) (Cubadda et al., 2020).

All analyses and graphs were performed by Microsoft Excel (2016) (Microsoft Corp. 365).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Seafood species

3.1.1. Essential elements

The concentrations of essential elements in the three poorly characterised species addressed in the present study – i.e. blue whiting, pouting, and common dab – are shown in Table 2. While many data are already available on these commonly farmed species, the same trace elements have been analysed in common carp and blue mussels as well for consistency and comparison (Table 2).

Blue mussels were the richest source of all elements, with the exception of iodine, which reached the highest concentration in pouting. To the best of our knowledge, the very high iodine content of pouting compared to other finfish, and more than two-fold that of blue mussel, has not been documented previously. On the other hand common dab was found to be low in iodine, with tissue levels similar to that of a freshwater fish such as common carp (see Table 2 and Barbosa et al., 2020), which is remarkable for a marine species. In general, common dab presented the lowest levels of all elements, excluding zinc and selenium, which appears to be similar to other species of the *Pleuronectidae* family and other demersal flatfish (Silva and Chamul, 2000; FAO, 2016).

In addition to the concentration in edible tissues, also the bioaccessibility of iodine, i.e. the extent to which the micronutrient is released from the food matrix after human digestion and becomes soluble and available for intestinal absorption, is important from a nutritional point of view. The bioaccessibility is likely to depend on iodine speciation, since iodide appears to be absorbed up to 100%, whereas organically bound iodine may be taken up at much smaller amounts (Hurrell, 1997; Jahreis et al., 2001). A low bioaccessibility of iodine from eggs (ca. 30%, Lipiec et al., 2012) and a variable bioaccessibility from fish (in a range from ca. 50 to ca. 90% depending on the species, with an average of 71%) (Alves et al., 2018) have been reported. In the present study, iodine bioaccessibility was assessed through a standardised *in vitro* model simulating human gastrointestinal digestion in blue whiting, the species having an intermediate iodine content. Three independent experiments gave a range of 97–99% and a mean of 98%, indicating that the trace element was readily accessible for intestinal absorption.

Next to iodine, selenium is another important nutrient of which seafood is generally a substantial source. Blue whiting, pouting, and common dab showed fairly high concentrations of selenium (0.26–0.33

Table 2

Concentrations of essential and non-essential trace elements in sustainable and underutilized seafood species (mean values and standard deviation in parenthesis).

Species	Essential elements (µg/g f.w.)					
	Ca	Cu	Fe	I	Se	Zn
<i>Micromesistius potassou</i>	281 (2)	0.42 (0.02)	2.29 (0.02)	0.15 (0.02)	0.30 (0.03)	4.60 (0.04)
<i>Limanda limanda</i>	160 (4)	0.12 (0.00)	0.64 (0.01)	<0.03 ^a	0.26 (0.05)	3.42 (0.01)
<i>Trisopterus luscus</i>	192 (46)	0.15 (0.00)	1.01 (0.03)	2.80 (0.77)	0.33 (0.08)	3.10 (0.06)
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	201 (104)	0.48 (0.01)	5.96 (0.05)	<0.03 ^a	0.23 (0.04)	4.71 (0.09)
<i>Mytilus edulis</i>	517 (7)	1.20 (0.03)	25.7 (1.0)	1.01 (0.12)	0.53 (0.04)	12.30 (0.20)
Species	Non-Essential elements (µg/g f.w.)					
	Cd	Hg	MeHg	%MeH ^c	Ni	Pb
<i>Micromesistius potassou</i>	0.0010 (0.0002)	0.027 (0.001)	0.026 (0.003)	96	0.040 (0.011)	<0.003 ^a
<i>Limanda limanda</i>	0.0005 (0.0002)	0.075 (0.001)	0.069 (0.002)	92	<0.012 ^a	<0.003 ^a
<i>Trisopterus luscus</i>	0.0004 (0.0001)	0.155 (0.002)	0.148 (0.002)	95	0.026 (0.002)	<0.003 ^a
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	0.0003 ^b	0.012 (0.000)	0.012 (0.001)	100	<0.012 ^a	<0.003 ^a
<i>Mytilus edulis</i>	0.0600 (0.0010)	0.025 (0.003)	0.010 (0.001)	40	0.155 (0.006)	0.128 (0.003)

^a LOD (3 independent samples below the LOD).

^b A single sample out of three was >LOQ.

^c Percentage of total mercury (Hg) present as methylmercury (MeHg).

µg/g f.w.), with values within an intermediate range between those of carp and of blue mussels. No studies have been identified documenting the selenium content of the three species. In general, almost no data are available in the literature on the content of the essential elements considered in the present study for the three poorly characterised species; the few available, referred to copper and zinc only, are in general agreement with those found in the present study (Table S11).

The intakes of essential elements from consumption of one daily portion (100 g) of the studied seafood species, expressed as the proportion of the DRVs (%) for the adult population, are shown in Table 3. The estimates assume that cooking would not lead to major changes in concentrations, which is consistent with literature data, with the only exception of boiling in the case of water-soluble elements (Dahl et al., 2020). The consumption of one portion of pouting and blue whiting contribute to >100% and 10% of the iodine AI for adults, respectively. For comparison, one portion of blue mussel provide 67% of the iodine AI for an adult (Table 3). Blue whiting, pouting, and common dab are good sources of selenium, with one portion providing 37–48% of the AI for adults. Mussels were confirmed to be excellent sources of iodine and iron, and also to provide iron and zinc at levels over 10% the respective DRVs.

3.1.2. Non-essential elements

Results are reported in Table 3. Mercury was present almost entirely as methylmercury in the four fish species (92–100% of total mercury). Pouting was the species with the highest methylmercury content. Although pouting are a relatively short lived species, they are scavengers which feed on the seabed (Table S1) and this might affect their methylmercury tissue levels. The total mercury concentration found in this study is almost identical to that reported in FAO/WHO (2011) for *Trisopterus* spp. (0.15 µg/g). A comparison with the mercury contents of European fish (mean, medium bound, of 53 species) (EFSA, 2012) shows that 56% of the listed fish species had higher mercury levels compared to pouting. Therefore, when put in the context of edible fish species in Europe, pouting should be considered as a species with an intermediate mercury burden. Methylmercury concentrations are half as much in common dab, which is in agreement with earlier studies (Table S12), and are very low in blue whiting (Table 3). For the latter species, whereas there is a good agreement with Azad et al. (2019), higher total mercury values can be found in the literature (Table S12). This is likely associated to the fact that this is a relatively long-lived species and large individuals, preying on small fish and cephalopods, are expected to reach greater methylmercury concentrations in muscle tissue compared to the smaller ones analysed in the present study. As expected, very low methylmercury concentrations were found in common carp. The same holds true for mussels, in which – differently from fish – 60% of the total mercury is in the form of inorganic mercury.

Cadmium, lead and nickel levels were remarkably low in all the fish species, whereas as expected they were 1–2 orders of magnitude greater in blue mussel, which is a suspension feeder prone to metal

bioaccumulation. Lead and nickel levels in mussels were in the intermediate-to-low range of values reported in other studies (Table S12); cadmium levels were in lowest range of reported values (Table S12), which might also be related to the clean room conditions and the strict quality control procedures applied in the analytical determinations performed within this study.

Mussels were also analysed for inorganic arsenic and the found concentration was 0.031 ± 0.001 µg/g f.w., i.e. in the expected range for this species (Cubadda et al., 2017; EFSA, 2021). Inorganic arsenic represented 1.6% of the total arsenic concentration (1.95 ± 0.02 µg/g f.w.).

Daily consumption of one portion of 100 g of the finfish species investigated in this study would result in exposure levels for the adult population equal to <1% of the TDI for nickel, <1% of the TWI for cadmium, ≤5% of the BMDL established for lead nephrotoxicity, <20% of the TWI for methylmercury (but up to 53% for common dab and 114% for pouting) (Table 4). Daily consumption of 100 g of mussels would result in higher exposure levels for inorganic arsenic and cadmium (up to 15% and 24%, respectively), whereas exposure to lead would exceed the BMDL considered leaving no room for a MOE, confirming the already known potential of this food item as a non-negligible contributor to chronic exposure for these toxic elements and element species (Table 4). Also in regard to acute nickel toxicity, mussel consumption leads to a lower MOE than the one recommended by EFSA, implying that a risk can not be excluded for the relevant population group, i.e. subjects with SCD.

3.1.3. Se:Hg molar ratios

Methylmercury is a potent neurotoxin especially affecting the developing brain, with unborn children constituting the most vulnerable group following dietary exposure of the mothers (EFSA, 2012a). It has long been postulated that selenium is able to interact with methylmercury *in vivo* and convert it into chemical species which are not bioavailable, thus decreasing the methylmercury body burden and associated toxicity. Recent evidence suggests that methylmercury, present as methylmercury-cysteinate (MeHgCys) in animal tissues including the skeletal muscle of fish, is demethylated in the form of HgSe and Hg(S,Se) granules, possibly via selenocysteinate (Hg(Sec)₄) complexes following interaction with selenoprotein P and selenoneine (Yamashita et al., 2013; Gajdosechova et al., 2016; Manceau et al., 2021). If selenium is present in molar excess in fish tissue, there will be sufficient selenoprotein P (and, in the species where it is abundant, selenoneine) available for sequestration of methylmercury. Therefore selenium:mercury molar ratios are important and are interpreted as a potential detoxification mechanism of the methylmercury taken up by seafood.

The Se:Hg molar ratios determined in the three key fish species investigated in this study ranged 5.4–28.7, with pouting showing the lowest value and blue whiting the highest (Fig. 1). Even greater Se:Hg molar ratios were found for common carp and mussels. These values fall (except for pouting) in the medium to upper range of reported values for

Table 3

Intake of essential elements from consumption of the sustainable and underutilized seafood species: proportion of the DRVs (%) supplied by one portion (100 g).

Species	Ca	Cu		Fe		I	Se	Zn	
		M ^a	F ^a	M ^a	F ^a			M ^a	F ^a
DRV for adults ^b	950 mg/day	1.6 mg/day	1.3 mg/day	16 mg/day	11 mg/day	150 µg/day	70 µg/day	11.7 mg/day	9.3 mg/day
<i>Micromesistius poutassou</i>	3	3	3	2	1	10	44	4	5
<i>Limanda limanda</i>	2	1	1	1	1	4	37	3	4
<i>Trisopterus luscus</i>	2	1	1	1	1	186	48	3	3
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	2	3	4	5	4	4	34	4	5
<i>Mytilus edulis</i>	5	8	9	23	16	67	76	11	13

^a M: males; F: females (for iron: premenopausal women).

^b For calcium, iron, zinc: population reference intakes (PRIs); for zinc, the PRI corresponding to a level of phytate intake of 600 mg/d is considered. For copper, iodine and selenium: adequate intakes (AIs).

Table 4

Exposure to non-essential elements from consumption of the sustainable and underutilized seafood species: proportion of the HBGVs (%) resulting from consumption of a 100-g portion.

Species	iAs	Cd	MeHg	Ni	Pb
HBGV for adults ^a	0.3 µg As/kg bw/day	2.5 µg Cd/kg bw/week	1.3 µg Hg/kg bw/week	Chronic, 13 µg Ni/kg bw/day Acute, 4.3 µg Ni/kg bw	0.63 µg Pb/kg bw/day
<i>Micromesistius poutassou</i>	–	0.4–0.4	18–20	0.4–0.4	35–40
<i>Limanda limanda</i>	–	0.2–0.2	46–53	0.1–0.1	10–12
<i>Trisopterus luscus</i>	–	0.2–0.2	99–114	0.3–0.3	23–26
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	–	0.1–0.1	8–9	0.1–0.1	10–12
<i>Mytilus edulis</i>	13–15	21–24	7–8	1–2	135–155

^a Lowest BMDL₀₁ for inorganic arsenic, TWI for cadmium and methylmercury, BMDL₀₁ for nephrotoxicity for lead, TDI for nickel chronic exposure, and LOAEL divided by a MOE of 30 for nickel acute exposure. The first value is for males, the second one is for females.

Fig. 1. Se:Hg molar ratio in the sustainable and underutilized seafood species.

a number of species; the value for pouting is distinctly higher than those found in fish with unfavourable ratios such as large predators (Alves et al., 2018; Azad et al., 2018; Teixeira et al., 2020). Therefore, selenium appears to be present in favourable amounts in relation to mercury tissue levels in all the five species.

3.2. Semi-industrial ready-to-eat products

3.2.1. Essential elements

The concentrations of essential elements in the RTE products are shown in Table 5, with the exception of the iodine content that has been assessed elsewhere (Oliveira et al., 2021). Beside fish and mussels, the products mainly contain vegetables and/or cereals and the resulting

Table 5

Concentrations of essential and non-essential trace elements in RTE products (mean values and standard deviation in parenthesis).

Product	Essential elements (µg/g f.w.)					Non-Essential elements (µg/g f.w.)		
	Ca	Cu	Fe	Se	Zn	Cd	Ni	Pb
FisBall_C	327 (8)	0.78 (0.03)	4.40 (0.28)	0.11 (0.03)	3.17 (0.17)	0.0015 (0.0002)	0.072 (0.031)	<0.003 ^a
FisSau_C	677 (146)	0.83 (0.05)	5.39 (0.36)	0.11 (0.02)	3.68 (0.11)	0.0025 (0.0001)	0.027 (0.004)	0.012 (0.009)
FisRou_P	540 (45)	0.46 (0.04)	3.92 (0.16)	0.10 (0.02)	3.76 (0.13)	0.0119 (0.0015)	0.060 (0.033)	<0.003 ^a
FisFil_P	1275 (327)	0.54 (0.03)	3.84 (0.43)	0.12 (0.03)	5.57 (0.48)	0.0112 (0.0013)	0.028 (0.002)	0.008 (0.001)
MusSou_S	522 (45)	1.11 (0.10)	10.46 (1.54)	0.13 (0.04)	5.92 (0.72)	0.0135 (0.0013)	0.225 (0.020)	0.017 (0.003)
FisBall_S	586 (34)	1.01 (0.06)	8.26 (0.53)	0.09 (0.01)	6.88 (0.57)	0.0070 (0.0013)	0.156 (0.019)	<0.003 ^a

^a LOD.

composition is due to the different ingredients and their proportions (Table 1). The calcium content is increased with respect to the starting fish/seafood raw materials and is notable for FisFil_P and FisSau_C. The contents of iron and copper are improved with respect to the fish raw materials (but are lower with respect to raw mussels). Zinc content is similar (but lower when compared to raw mussels), selenium is decreased but still present at substantial concentrations.

The intake of essential elements from consumption of one portion (250 g) of the RTE products has been related to the DRVs established for the targeted population groups, i.e. children aged 8–10 years (FisBall_C, FisSau_C), pregnant women (FisRou_P, FisFil_P), and seniors (MusSou_S, FisBall_S), and the ratio is presented as percentage in Fig. 2.

For children, consumption of one portion of FisBall_C and FisSau_C almost meet the selenium daily requirement, providing ca. 80% of the AI. However, all the RTE products are excellent sources of selenium for

Fig. 2. Intake of essential elements from consumption of the innovative RTE products: proportion of the DRVs (%) supplied by one portion (250 g).

the respective population groups.

FisFil_P is a valuable source of calcium for pregnant women, and FisSau_C for children. MusSou_S, FisBall_S are good sources of iron for seniors. Many other RTE items provide >15% of the relevant DRV (e.g. FisBall_S in the case of zinc, and FisBall_C, FisSau_C, MusSou_S, and FisBall_S in the case of copper).

It is worth mentioning that these same RTE products were designed to meet the nutritional requirements of children and pregnant women for iodine, EPA and DHA, of seniors for protein and vitamin, and of the three above-mentioned target populations for vitamin D and vitamin E. In a separate study, they were experimentally confirmed to be effective in meeting these requirements (see the companion paper: [Oliveira et al., 2021](#)).

3.2.2. Non-essential elements

The concentrations of the non-essential elements in the RTE products are shown in [Table 5](#), with the exception of the mercury content that has been assessed elsewhere ([Oliveira et al., 2021](#)).

All the RTE products have low concentrations of cadmium and lead ([Table 5](#)). Nickel levels are generally in the medium to low range when compared to other foods, e.g. based on the results of recent TDS studies ([Cubadda et al., 2020](#)), with the partial exception of the products aimed at seniors.

The RTE foods containing mussels as ingredients, i.e. MusSou_S and Extrasou_S, were also analysed for inorganic arsenic and the found concentrations were $0.007 \pm 0.001 \mu\text{g/g}$ f.w. in both cases, which represent very low levels when compared with occurrence levels from recent TDS studies ([Cubadda et al., 2016](#)) or recent EFSA estimates ([EFSA, 2021](#)). Inorganic arsenic amounted to 1.1% and 0.9% of the total arsenic concentration in the two items ($0.67 \pm 0.06 \mu\text{g/g}$ f.w. and $0.78 \pm 0.12 \mu\text{g/g}$ f.w. respectively).

Daily consumption of one portion of the RTE products would result in exposure levels for the adult population equal to $\leq 6\%$ of the TDI for nickel, $\leq 8\%$ of the lowest BMDL for inorganic arsenic (mussel-containing items), $\leq 14\%$ of the TWI for cadmium ($\leq 19\%$ for Extrasou_S), $\leq 32\%$ of the BMDL established for lead nephrotoxicity (but equal to $< 52\%$ for Extrasou_S, $\leq 67\%$ for MusSou_S, $\leq 113\%$ for FisSau_C). When acute nickel toxicity in subjects with SCD was considered, a potential issue was identified for MusSou_S (and the linked product Extrasou_S), FisBall_S, FisBall_C, and, to a lesser extent, for FisSau_C and FisRou_P, since exposure would lead to a lower MOE than the one recommended by EFSA (i.e. 30).

4. Conclusions

Underutilized and sustainable seafood species can be employed as valuable protein sources providing important micronutrients while preventing high exposures to methylmercury and other contaminants. The present study produced initial data to characterize the profile of three such fish species in terms of essential and toxic elements. All have been found to be rich sources of selenium. Pouting, and to a lesser extent blue whiting, are good sources of iodine. The bioaccessibility of iodine in blue whiting was shown to be remarkably high (98%). In addition, the three species were found to have markedly favourable selenium:mercury molar ratios and present sufficiently low levels of methylmercury; pouting (i.e. the species with the highest content) showed an intermediate methylmercury concentration compared to other fish species consumed in Europe.

Innovative semi-industrial RTE products manufactured using these fish species (or otherwise sustainable species) as raw materials and designed to meet the requirements of key nutrients such as iodine and n-3 LCPUFA of children, pregnant women and seniors, were shown in the present study to be valuable sources of other essential elements, including selenium, calcium, iron and copper. The results on RTE products were not a cause of concern in regard of chronic intakes of methylmercury, inorganic arsenic, cadmium, and nickel. The lead levels,

and the resulting exposure, in the mussel-containing RTE products as well as the potential for acute intake of nickel are issues that may deserve further attention.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Francesca Ferraris: Investigation, Validation, Writing – original draft. **Francesca Iacoponi:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Andrea Raggi:** Investigation, Validation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Francesca Baldi:** Investigation, Validation. **Murielle Fretigny:** Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Alberto Mantovani:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Francesco Cubadda:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. All authors read and agreed with the submitted version of the manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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References

- Alves, R.N., Maulvault, A.L., Barbosa, V.L., Fernandez-Tejedor, M., Tediosi, A., Kotterman, M., van den Heuvel, F.H.M., Robbins, J., Fernandes, J.O., Romme Rasmussen, R., Sloth, J.J., Marques, A., 2018. Oral bioaccessibility of toxic and essential elements in raw and cooked commercial seafood species available in European markets. *Food Chem.* 267, 15–27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2017.11.045>.
- Azad, A.M., Frantzen, S., Bank, M.S., Nilsen, B.M., Duinker, A., Madsen, L., Maage, A., 2019. Effects of geography and species variation on selenium and mercury molar ratios in Northeast Atlantic marine fish communities. *Sci. Total Environ.* 652, 1482–1496. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.405>.
- Barbosa, V., Luísa, A., Anacleto, P., Santos, M., Mai, M., Oliveira, H., Delgado, I., Coelho, I., Barata, M., Araújo, R., Ribeiro, L., Eljasik, P., Sadowski, J., Tórz, A., Panic, R., Dias, J., Pousão-ferreira, P., Luísa, M., Martins, M., 2020. Enriched feeds with iodine and selenium from natural and sustainable sources to modulate farmed gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) and common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) filets elemental nutritional value. *Food Chem. Toxicol.* 140 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2020.111330>.
- Bogard, J.R., Farmery, A.K., Little, D.C., Fulton, E.A., Cook, M., n.d. Comment Will fish be part of future healthy and sustainable diets? *Lancet Planet. Heal.* 3, e159–e160. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(19\)30018-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(19)30018-X).
- Cubadda, F., D'Amato, M., Aureli, F., Raggi, A., Mantovani, A., 2016. Dietary exposure of the Italian population to inorganic arsenic: the 2012–2014 Total Diet Study. *Food Chem. Toxicol.* 98, 148–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2016.10.015>.
- Cubadda, F., Jackson, B.P., Cottingham, K.L., Van Horne, Y.O., Kurzius-Spencer, M., 2017. Human exposure to dietary inorganic arsenic and other arsenic species: state of knowledge, gaps and uncertainties. *Sci. Total Environ.* 579, 1228–1239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.11.108>.
- Cubadda, F., Iacoponi, F., Ferraris, F., D'Amato, M., Aureli, F., Raggi, A., Sette, S., Turrini, A., Mantovani, A., 2020. Dietary exposure of the Italian population to nickel: the national Total Diet Study. *Food Chem. Toxicol.* 146, 111813. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2020.111813>.
- Dahl, L., Duinker, A., Naess, S., Markhus, M.W., Nerhus, I., Midtbo, L.K., Kjellekvold, M., 2020. Iodine and mercury content in raw, boiled, pan-fried, and oven-baked atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*). *Foods* 9, 1652.

- EEA, 2016. EEA Report No 25/2016. Seafood in Europe: A Food System Approach for Sustainability. European Environment Agency. <https://doi.org/10.2800/06589>.
- EFSA, 2017. Dietary Reference Values for Nutrients. Summary Report. EFSA supporting publication, p. e15121. <https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2017.e15121>, 98 pp.
- EFSA, Arcella, D., Cascio, C., Gomez Ruiz, J.A., 2021. Scientific report on the chronic dietary exposure to inorganic arsenic. EFSA Journal 19 (1), 6380. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2021.6380>, 50 pp.
- EFSA CONTAM Panel, 2009a. Scientific opinion on arsenic in food. EFSA Journal 7 (10), 1351. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2009.1351>, 199 pp.
- EFSA CONTAM Panel, 2009b. Scientific Opinion on a request from the European Commission on cadmium in food. EFSA Journal 980, 1–139.
- EFSA CONTAM Panel, 2010. Scientific opinion on lead in food. EFSA Journal 8 (4), 1570. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2010.1570> [151 pp.].
- EFSA CONTAM Panel, 2012. Scientific Opinion on the risk for public health related to the presence of mercury and methylmercury in food. EFSA Journal 10 (12), 2985. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2012.2985> [241 pp.].
- EFSA CONTAM Panel, Schrenk, D., Bignami, M., Bodin, L., Chipman, J.K., del Mazo, J., Grasl-Kraupp, B., Hogstrand, C., Hoogenboom, L.R., Leblanc, J.-C., Nebbia, C.S., Ntzani, E., Petersen, A., Sand, S., Schwerdtle, T., Vleminckx, C., Wallace, H., Guerin, T., Massanyi, P., Van Loveren, H., Baert, K., Gergelova, P., Nielsen, E., 2020. Scientific Opinion on the update of the risk assessment of nickel in food and drinking water. EFSA Journal 18 (11), 6268. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6268>, 101 pp.
- EFSA NDA Panel, 2014. Scientific Opinion on health benefits of seafood (fish and shellfish) consumption in relation to health risks associated with exposure to methylmercury. EFSA Journal 12 (7), 3761. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2014.3761>, 80 pp.
- EFSA Scientific Committee, 2012. Guidance on selected default values to be used by the EFSA Scientific Committee, Scientific Panels and Units in the absence of actual measured data [32 pp.]. EFSA Journal 10 (3), 2579. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2012.2579>. Available online. www.efsa.europa.eu.
- EFSA Scientific Committee, 2015. Statement on the benefits of fish/seafood consumption compared to the risks of methylmercury in fish/seafood. EFSA Journal 13 (1), 3982. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2015.3982>, 36 pp.
- FAO, 2016. FAO/INFOODS global food composition database for fish and shellfish version 1.0 - uFiSh1.0. Rome, Italy. Available at: <http://aims.fao.org/activity/blog/faoinfoods-global-food-composition-database-fish-and-shellfish-data-policy>.
- FAO, 2020. The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2020. Sustainability in action, Rome. <https://doi.org/10.4060/ca9229en>.
- Gajdosechova, Z., Lawan, M.M., Urgast, D.S., Raab, A., Scheckel, K.G., Lombi, E., Kopittke, P.M., Loeschner, K., Larsen, E.H., Woods, G., Brownlow, A., Read, F.L., Feldmann, J., Krupp, E.M., 2016. *In vivo* formation of natural HgSe nanoparticles in the liver and brain of pilot whales. Sci. Rep. 6, 34361. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep34361>.
- HLPE, 2014. Sustainable Fisheries and Aquaculture for Food Security and Nutrition. A Report by the High Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition of the Committee on. World Food Security, Rome.
- Hurrell, R.F., 1997. Bioavailability of iodine. Eur. J. Clin. Nutr. 51, 9–12.
- Jahreis, G., Hausmann, W., Kiessling, G., Leiterer, M., 2001. Bioavailability of iodine from normal diets rich in dairy products - results of balance studies in women. Exp. Clin. Endocrinol. Diabetes 109, 163–167. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-2001-14840>.
- Lipiec, E., Warowicka, O., Ruzik, L., Zhou, Y., Jarosz, M., Polec-Pawlak, k., 2012. Investigation of iodine bioavailability from chicken eggs versus iodized kitchen salt with *in vitro* method. Eur. Food Res. Technol. 234, 913–919. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00217-012-1693-z>.
- Manceau, A., Bourdineaud, J.P., Oliveira, R.B., Sarrazin, S.L.F., Krabbenhoft, D.P., Eagles-Smith, C.A., Ackerman, J.T., Stewart, A.R., Ward-Deitrich, C., Del Castillo Busto, M.E., Goenaga-Infante, H., Wack, A., Retegan, M., Detlefs, B., Glatzel, P., Bustamante, P., Nagy, K.L., Poulin, B.A., 2021. Demethylation of methylmercury in bird, fish, and earthworm. Environ. Sci. Technol. 55, 1527–1534. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c04948>.
- Minckus, M., Alminger, M., Alvito, P., Ballance, S., Bohn, T., Bourlieu, C., Carriere, F., Boutrou, R., Corredig, M., Dupont, D., Dufour, C., Egger, L., Golding, M., Karakaya, S., Kirkhus, B., Le Feunteun, S., Lesmes, U., Macierzanka, A., Mackie, A., Marze, S., McClements, D.J., Menard, O., Recio, I., Santos, C.N., Singh, R.P., Vegarud, G.E., Wickham, M.S.J., Weitschies, W., Brodtkorb, A., 2014. A standardised static *in vitro* digestion method suitable for food – an international consensus. Food Funct 5, 1113. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3fo60702j>.
- Oliveira, H., Bloquel, C., Santos, M., Fretigny, M., Correia, T., Gonçalves, A., Cabado, A. G., Blanco López, L., Raaholte, B.W., Ferraris, F., Iacoponi, F., Cubadda, F., Mantovani, A., Vallet, E., Vlaemyneck, G., Fernández-Arribas, J., Eljarrat, E., López, E., López de Aldai, M., Panicz, R., Sobczak, M., Eljasik, P., Cunha, S., Ferreira, R., Fernandes, J.O., Sousa, S., Domingues, V.F., Delerue-Matos, C., Marques, A., Leonor Nunes, M., 2021. Semi-industrial development of nutritious and healthy seafood dishes from sustainable species. Food Chem. Toxicol. 155, 112431.
- Silva, J.L., Chamul, S., 2000. Composition of marine and freshwater finfish and shellfish species and their products. In: Martin, Roy E., Paine Carter, Emily, Flick, George J., Davis, Lynn M. (Eds.), Marine and Freshwater Products Handbook. CRC Press, pp. 31–45. Jr.
- Teixeira, G., Raimundo, J., Goulart, J., Costa, V., Menezes, G.M., Caetano, M., 2020. Hg and Se composition in demersal deep-sea fish from the North-East Atlantic. Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res. 27, 33649–33657. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-08970-3>.
- Thomsen, S.T., Assunção, R., Afonso, C., Boué, G., Cardoso, C., Cubadda, F., Garre, F., Krusselbrink, J.W., Mantovani, A., Pitter, J.G., Poulsen, M., Verhagen, H., Ververis, E., van der Voet, H., Watzl, B., Pires, S.M., 2021. Human health risk-benefit assessment of fish and seafood: a scoping review. Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2021.1915240>. Online ahead of print.
- WHO & FAO, 2011. Report of the joint FAO/WHO expert consultation on the risks and benefits of fish consumption. FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Report No. 978. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/44666>.
- Yamashita, M., Yamashita, Y., Suzuki, T., 2013. Selenoneine, a novel selenium-containing compound, mediates detoxification mechanisms against methylmercury accumulation and toxicity in zebrafish embryo. Mar. Biotechnol. 15, 559–570. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10126-013-9508-1>.